

**Studies in Nuclear Magnetic Resonance.
The Kinetics of Protonation of Aliphatic Amines**

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NUCLEAR magnetic resonance spectroscopy provides a powerful and direct tool for the measurement of fast exchange rates. Grunwald, Loewenstein, and Meiboom^{1,2}, developed a method to give quantitative results for the protolysis kinetics of methyl, dimethyl, and trimethylammonium chloride in aqueous solutions. The equilibria can be represented schematically by :

where, R, represents either a methyl group or a hydrogen.

Grunwald, Loewenstein, and Meiboom¹, have considered the following possible mechanisms :

The total rate constant for the overall reaction is given by :

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{(R-NH_3^+)} = K_1 + K_2 \cdot K_W / (H^+) + (K_3 + K_4) \cdot K \cdot (R-NH_2) / (H^+) \quad (5)$$

where, $K_W = (H^+)(HO^-)$,
and $K_A = (H^+)(R-NH_2) / (R-NH_3^+)$

From measurements of the -CH₂-, or CH-multiplets at different values of (H⁺) and (R-NH₃⁺), values for K₁, K₂, and (K₃ + K₄) are obtained. From the measurements of the broadening of the water line, separation of the latter into K₃ and K₄ is accomplished. Results on the protolysis reactions of ethyl-, diethyl-, triethyl-, isopropyl-, isobutyl-, and neopentylammonium ions are reported.

Experimental

Kinetic Measurements : Rate of exchange was measured by the nuclear magnetic resonance technique. A varian associate high resolution NMR spectrometer was used at 56.45 Mc/sec. In all the amines studied, there are other groups in the molecule which could interact with the protons on the carbon atom next to the NH₃⁺ group, thus complicating the observed spectra. The procedure adopted in this case was to decouple the protons next to the NH₃⁺ from other groups in the

molecule. Thus we could obtain simple doublets, triplets and quadruplets, from which the rate constants were measured. Spectra typical of those used in the final rate determination are shown in Figs. (1) and (2); also are shown in the figure typical spectra of the uncoupled nuclei. The NMR measurements were made in an air-conditioned room. During any one measurement, the variation in temperature was less than 1°. Most of the measurements were made at 20° ± 0.5°.

Measurement of rate constants. An outline of the methods of calculation as adopted to the case of methyl, dimethyl, and trimethylammonium ions, has been given by Grunwald, Loewenstein, and Meiboom¹, and Loewenstein and Meiboom⁴.

Fig. 1. Coupled and uncoupled signals of ethylammonium chloride, 3.44M at pH 0.08 (above), 3.23 (below).

Fig. 2. Coupled and uncoupled signals in isopropylammonium chloride, 5.61M at pH. 2.36.

Results and Discussion

A summary of rate processes in dilute aqueous acid is shown in Table 1. Rate constants for the various possible mechanisms of amine protolysis are presented in Tables 2 to 6. In principle, all rate constants are

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF RATE PROCESSES IN DILUTE AQUEOUS ACID

Reaction	Rate Constant
$RNH_3^+ + H_2O$	K_1 (sec. ⁻¹)
$RNH_2 + H_3O^+$	K_{-1} (sec. ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)
$RNH_3^+ + OH^-$	K_2 (sec. ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)
$RNH_2 + H_2O$	K_{-2} (sec. ⁻¹)
$RNH_3^+ + H_2NR$	K_3 (sec. ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)
$RNH_3^+ + H_2O + H_2NR$	K_4 (sec. ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)

NOTES

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF K_1^+ AND K_{-1} FOR AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF ALKYLAMMONIUM IONS AT 20°

Compound	$[\text{RNH}_3^+]\text{M}$	$10^{11}K_A$	K_1^+	$10^{11}K_{-1}$	P
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	7.24	1.182	5.76	8.82	0.33
	4.83	1.20	5.85	8.66	0.32
	3.44	1.23	6.02	8.43	0.34
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^+$	4.04	0.57	5.33	16.42	0.30
	3.50	0.57	5.40	16.22	0.32
	2.02	0.60	5.62	15.60	0.33
	1.80	0.61	5.67	15.44	0.32
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}^+$	1.95	1.15	6.91	8.59	0.29
	1.77	1.15	5.93	8.55	0.32
	1.60	1.16	5.97	8.51	0.31
$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CHNH}_3^+$	5.61	1.31	1.17	1.59	0.32
	3.44	1.34	1.19	1.55	0.35
	2.58	1.37	1.22	1.52	0.30
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	4.47	2.16	2.12	1.73	0.33
	3.68	2.18	2.13	1.71	0.41
	3.11	2.22	2.19	1.69	0.63
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	3.85	1.81	3.91	3.77	0.20
	3.68	1.82	3.93	3.76	0.18
	2.94	1.85	3.98	3.71	0.22

P, is the fraction of protolysis involving direct proton transfer from NH_3^+ to H_2O

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS FOR PROTON TRANSFER REACTIONS IN WATER AT 20°

Reactions	$A_0(\text{Ohm}^{-1})$	$10^{-10}K_5(\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1})$	$10^{-5}K_{-5}(\text{sec}^{-1})$
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	252.55	3.66	170.5
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^+$	249.35	3.61	361.4
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}^+$	252.20	3.66	191.5

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF K_1^0 AND K_2^0 FOR AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF ALKYLAMMONIUM IONS AT 20°

Compound	$10^{11}K_0^A$	$10^{-11}K_0^0(\text{sec}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1})$	$K_1^0(\text{sec}^{-1})$
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	2.14	4.87 ± 0.62	10.43 ± 1.33
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^+$	1.00	9.36 ± 0.86	9.36 ± 0.86
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}^+$	1.91	5.16 ± 0.22	9.85 ± 0.40
$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CHNH}_3^+$	2.34	0.89 ± 0.05	2.08 ± 0.12
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	3.80	0.98 ± 0.12	3.73 ± 0.46
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	3.16	2.16 ± 0.12	6.84 ± 0.35

TABLE 5—RATE CONSTANTS K_0 AND K_1 FOR PROTON TRANSFER REACTIONS OF ALKYLAMMONIUM IONS IN WATER AT 20°

IN $\text{SEC}^{-1}\text{M}^{-1}$.

Compound	$10^{-8}(K_0^0 + K_1^0)$	$10^{-8}K_0^0$	$10^{-8}K_1^0$	pK _A
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	21.49 ± 0.58	14.28 ± 0.19	7.21 ± 0.39	10.67
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^+$	23.75 ± 0.66	16.19 ± 0.55	7.56 ± 0.11	11.00
$(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}^+$	24.54 ± 0.55	16.96 ± 8.16	7.58 ± 0.19	10.72
$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{CHNH}_3^+$	9.9 ± 0.12	6.71 ± 0.04	3.20 ± 0.09	10.63
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	10.15 ± 0.24	5.51 ± 0.10	4.65 ± 0.14	10.42
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CCH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	25.14 ± 0.21	20.08 ± 0.21	5.06 ± 0.80	10.50

TABLE 6—RATE MEASUREMENT BASED ON THE BROADENING OF THE NH_3 -TRIPLET.

Compound	$[\text{RNH}_3^+]\text{M}$	(3 π slope*(obs.))	(3 π slope (calc.))
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_3^+$	4.83	0.174 ∓ 0.003	0.172 ∓ 0.002
	3.44	0.123 ∓ 0.02	0.124 ∓ 0.00

* Slope of the plot of half-width of the nitrogen line vs, $1/(\text{H}^+)$ in the range of initial broadening, calculated by the least-square method.

functions of the ammonium ion concentrations. Therefore, a number of measurements were made in which the alkylammonium ion concentration was constant, and the hydrogen ion concentration varied from 10^{-8} to $10^{-5} M$.

The exchange reactions considered in this study are the ones given by Grunwald, Loewenstein, and Meiboom¹. The two major mechanisms for protolysis of aqueous alkylammonium ions are reactions 3 and 4. The simplest mechanisms for reaction 4, are as follows: (a) Proton transfer from $R-NH_3^+$ to H_2O , followed rapidly by proton transfer to $R-NH_2$; (b) Concerted transfer of both protons; and (c) Proton transfer from H_2O to $R-NH_3^+$, followed rapidly by release of a proton from $R-NH_3^+$. Mechanism (a) can be ruled out because the rate is not expected to be much faster than that of reaction (1), and hence much slower than the observed rate (K_4). In mechanism (b), the rate determining step is either the reorientation of the water molecule between the alkylammonium ion and alkylamine so as to permit the concerted proton transfer or it is the proton transfer itself. In the former, the rate should depend on the extent of reorientation. In mechanism (c), the electrostatic field of the ion is expected to increase the acid strength of the adjacent water molecules by, at least, a few orders of magnitude⁵. The increase of the acid strength of the water facilitates the proton transfer to the alkylamine and the observed magnitude of K_4 is reasonably relative to the values of K_{-2} listed in Table 3. Since, the field produced by the ion at the nearest water molecules is the same for NH_4^+ and $CH_3CH_2NH_3^+$, the rate should parallel the base strength of the proton-accepting amine as is observed. Thus mechanism (c) is most consistent with the experimental facts.

It is interesting to compare the trend of the rate constants with the pK_a values, because the latter give some measure of the proton donating capacity of the ion. Table 4, shows that K_1 increases as pK_a decreases (i.e.), as the ion becomes a stronger acid, and is more capable of donating its exchangeable protons to water. In the series, ethyl, diethyl-, and triethylammonium ions, ethylammonium ion has the smallest pK_a value, and it has a lower K_1 than di-, and triethylammonium ion. Triethylammonium ion has a higher K_1 than diethylammonium ion, as would be expected from the small-value of pK_a for the former. The value of K_4 has no correlation with pK_a . In the above series of the three ammonium ions, ethylammonium ion has a much lower K_4 than would be expected from its low pK_a .

It is interesting to compare the basicity of ethyl and isopropylamines in which we have introduced another methyl group at the α -carbon atom. If the inductive effect alone was the only important factor in determining the basicity of alkylamines, isopropylamine would be the stronger base. In fact, it is a weaker base than ethylamine, and this suggests that other factors such as hydrogen bonding with water molecules and electrostatic interactions^{6,7,8} are very important in determining the basicity of alkylamines.

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Chemical Constituents of the Leaves of *Callicarpa macrophylla* Vahl.

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CALLICARPA *macrophylla* (Verbenaceae) grows in the Himalayan region. It is used in the treatment of stomach disorder^{1,2} and biological transformation to gibberellins³. The recent report⁴⁻⁶ on the isolation of calliterpenone and its monoacetate¹⁻⁶, β -sitosterol, ursolic acid and 7-*o*-glucuronides of luteolin and apigenin⁶ from the same plant prompted us to publish our work on the chemical examination of the leaves of the plant. We have encountered the ethyl ester of C_{23} -fatty acid, free C_{22} , C_{23} and C_{24} -fatty acids, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside, calliterpenone, calliterpenone monoacetate, ursolic acid, 2 α -hydroxyursolic acid and crategolic acid. Dried and powdered leaves of *C. macrophylla* were percolated with rectified spirit and the extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions.

Neutral fraction:

Ethyl ester of $C_{22}H_{44}COOH$: The neutral fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) afforded a clear oil, $C_{25}H_{50}O_2$, b. p. $135^\circ-137^\circ/0.5$ mm of Hg, which is found to be the Ethyl ester of $C_{22}H_{44}COOH$. I.R. 1740 and 1240 cm^{-1} . NMR. Signals at 4.14 (2H, dd, $J=6$ Hz, $-O,CH_2$, CH_2), 2.29 (2H, t, $-CO$, CH_2), 1.25 (4OH, s) and 0.90 (6H, t, $J=6$ Hz, two terminal CH_3). (Found: C, 78.60; H, 12.95. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{50}O_2$: C, 78.47, H, 13.17%).